

samples 1 d before and after insecticide application. Each board was examined under a dissecting microscope.

Cypermethrin and cis-2-cypermethrin caused WBPH resurgence. Cis-2-cypermethrin caused BPH resurgence and hopperburn, and reduced yield 28% below that of the unsprayed control (Table 1). Carbofuran and BPMC gave

good control of both planthoppers.

When changes in populations of spiders, Coleoptera, mirid predators, and egg parasitoids were considered, the decline in spider populations was closely related to WBPH and BPH resurgence. Both pyrethroids were highly toxic to spiders, contributing to high hopper nymphspider ratios early in the period

of hopper population increase (Table 2).

Carbamates were less toxic to spiders and other natural enemies. Carbofuran and BPMC gave moderate or poor control of most other rice pests. Both pyrethroids gave excellent control of other rice pests and tested doses were not toxic to fish. *ℵ*

Gall midge (GM) activity and parasitization by *Platygaster oryzae* in Jaya stubble and wild rice at Bhubaneswar, India

B. C. Jena, entomologist, Regional Research Station, Semiliguda (Sunabeda), Koraput, Orissa; and N. C. Patnaik and N. Panda, Entomology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology (OUAT), Bhubaneswar, India

GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) breeds in Jaya rice stubble during the off-season (Jan-Jun) and also in wild rice *Oryza perennis* (Moench). GM-infested tillers turn into silvershoots or galls which protrude from the leaf whorl (exposed galls). In unproductive and late formed tillers, many galls do not protrude from the leaf whorl and remain hidden in the culm (suppressed galls).

We studied GM abundance, activity, and parasitization due to *Platygaster oryzae* (Cameron) in Jaya rice stubble and in wild rice at OUAT in 1982.

Stubble was left in unsprayed fields planted to Jaya after harvesting the wet season crop (Jul-Dec). It was occasionally irrigated to encourage ratoon growth. Fields were divided into four quadrats and each quadrat into five subplots. From each subplot, one hill was uprooted at random at weekly intervals. In the laboratory, silvershoot infestation was recorded and the exposed and suppressed galls were dissected to determine parasitization. Twenty randomly selected hills of wild rice were collected weekly from swamps adjoining the Jaya fields and examined for midge attack and parasitization.

Gall midge was prevalent in Jaya stubble throughout the off-season, peaking at 17 wk (23-29 Apr). Parasitization peaked at 5 and 6 wk

Exposed and suppressed galls and parasitization of Jaya stubble and *O. perennis*, Bhubaneswar, India.

(29 Jan-11 Feb). Suppressed galls were maximum at 15 wk (9-15 Apr) (see figure).

O. perennis also harbored GM throughout the year, but infestation was lower than in stubble. Parasitization,

however, was higher. Gall occurrence was highest in the 3d (15-21 Jan) and 46th wk (12-18 Nov) and most galls were suppressed. GM infestation and parasitization followed a wax and wane cycle. *ℵ*

Stem injury in deep water rice as a guide for determining stem borer (SB) infestation at different growth stages

S.K. Datta, D. Konar, S.K. De, and P.K. Banerjee, Operational Research Project, Pandua, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

SB *Scirpophaga incertulas* infestation generally is high in deep water rice. We

studied SB infestation at different internodes of deep water rice plants at harvest. Water level, plant height, stem elongation, internode formation, and growth phase were considered.

A 0.2-ha deep water field was planted to photoperiod-sensitive Jaladhi 1 in early Jun 1983. Soil was a clay loam with pH 7.0-7.5. At land preparation, 10 t farmyard manure/ha was applied. Standard cultivation methods were

practiced, and harvest was in late Dec.

Water depth was recorded weekly. SB were caught daily from 1800 to 2200 h in a light trap 200 m from the field. Each morning the catch was recorded. The first SB were trapped the 2d wk of Jul (see figure). Population increased rapidly between late Sep and late Oct, then declined. Every 2 wk, 10 plants were randomly collected and height, stem length, and number of internodes of the main shoot were recorded. At harvest, 140 plant samples were collected, and percent SB damage at different internodes of the main stem was recorded (see figure).

Almost no SB were trapped at early seedling growth when soil was dry. During early elongation (Jul-Sep), when almost all of the stems were submerged, SB infested few plants. Peak SB infestation was at preflowering. At harvest, damage was low in the 13th internode, but was substantially higher in the last 3 internodes (see figure).

Data on peak SB emergence reflect the period of maximum plant infestation. Also, SB infestation increases with decreasing water level. *ℳ*

Percent SB-damaged internodes (base to apex) of deep water rice plants at harvest and variations of light trap catch, water level, plant height, stem length, and number of internodes, West Bengal, India.

Stem borer infestation on hybrid rice

Chieng Chienyun, research assistant, Plant Protection Institute, Hunan Academy of Agricultural Science (HAAS), Changsa, China

Hybrid rice was released in China in 1978. Since then, striped stem borer (SSB) *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) and yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* damage has increased. SSB attacks rice in Hunan, Jiangxi, Jiangsu, Zhejiang, and Sichuan Provinces, and YSB damages rice in southern Jiangxi and Fujian, and northern Guangdong.

In surveys at the HAAS farm beginning in 1978, we found that SSB populations in hybrid rice fields were 28 to 36% higher than in other rice fields and that there were 107 to 170% more egg masses. There are 7 to 17 times as many YSB egg mass as in other rice fields.

Survival rates of SSB larvae during 3 yr were 8, 18, and 19% higher on hybrid than on other rices, and YSB larvae survival was 13 to 20% higher. Larvae and pupae of SSB that fed on hybrid rice weighed 17 and 13% more than those collected from other rices. The mean weights over 2 yr of SSB pupae that fed on hybrid rice were 30 and 32% higher than the weights of those that fed on other rices. The first year, SSB females grown on hybrid rice produced 46 to 103 eggs/female; in the second and third years, they produced 46 to 82 more eggs/female than SSB females reared on other rices.

YSB larvae reared on hybrid rice weighed an average 63 mg. Those reared on other rices weighed an average 51 mg. YSB females produced an average 262 eggs/female on hybrid rice and 224 eggs/female on other rices. Over 4 yr, YSB hibernating on hybrid rice had 89,

23, 40, and 46% mortality vs 11, 9, 21, and 24% on other rices.

Most hybrid rice lines have large stems, heavy foliage, thick sheath, and long duration, which may favor SSB and YSB development. *ℳ*

The correct name of the African rice stem-boring Diopsidae (stalk-eyed fly)

H.R. Feijen. Plant Protection Scheme Zanzibar, P.O. Box 1062, Zanzibar, Tanzania

In the 1950s a stalk-eyed fly (Diopsidae) was identified as an important rice stem borer in Africa. The fly became known as *Diopsis thoracica* Westwood, 1837. Subsequently most authors wrote that *thoracica* was a junior synonym of *Diopsis macrophthalma* Dalman, 1817, which had *Diopsis longicornis*